

Digital Marketing & Social Media

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Abstract:

Nowadays social media has become an easy and cheap way not only to connect people but also to get customers. But, for that we should be able to use it properly. So it is important to understand how social media is used for marketing and advertising. For that, let us assume that we have a business of fashionable dresses as an example. To digitalize your business with the help of social media, you first have to create an account in the name of the business on various social sites. Then you can add photos, videos, offers, sales etc. of your products. You can attract customers by providing information, giving them the option to choose or inquire about the dresses of their choice from the comfort of their homes, and you will build a relationship of trust with your customers. So your business can increase. This is what we call social media marketing. We can use the option of social media advertising to reach our business to new customers. In this we can advertise our new products or sales on social media, so that our business reaches more people and our sales can increase. We can reach maximum number of people with very low cost on social media

Key Words: Digital Marketing, Social Media, Facebook, Tweeter, Instagram

Introduction:

Social media marketing is the use of social media platforms and websites to promote a product or service. Although the terms e-marketing and digital marketing are still used in academia, social media marketing is becoming more popular with both practitioners and researchers. Many social media platforms have built-in data analytics tools that enable companies to track the success and investment of ad campaigns. Companies address multiple stakeholders through social media marketing.

This includes current and potential customers, current and potential employees, journalists, bloggers and the general public. At the strategic level, social media marketing involves defining the marketing campaign, administration, scope and establishing the firm's desired social media culture. When using social media marketing, companies can allow consumers and Internet users to post user-generated content instead of using marketing-ready ad copy known as Armenia.

Objective and Method of Study:

This Study is an attempt on highlight meaning, Features and Significance of Social Media Marketing, growing importance of the Social Media Marketing, Growth of Social Media Marketing. This Study is of descriptive method. Secondary data collected form Internet, Government Documents, newspaper, books, Research paper and Research report.

Marketing Importance of Social Media:

- The social media marketing process creates and sustains recognition of the business brand or brand in the public mind and can lead to customer loyalty towards it.
- New customer class can be easily formed through this type of marketing medium.

Likewise, you can keep in touch with current or past customers. Social media is very popular. Many people are communicating through it, internet network is also available almost everywhere. This makes it easy to reach all the people and can create a new customer segment.

- Social media marketing saves time and cost of marketing. Within a short period of time, one can easily reach the country and abroad and the cost is also very low. A very attractive message can be created with the help of audio-visual media.
- By using these media in marketing, customer feedback can be recorded immediately. It can be understood and sales are planned keeping in mind the response. When there was no social media, such responses could not be recorded. But now it is easily possible. Based on this information, a new strategy can be devised. It also understands what the customers think about the business or the product.
- The country has a large youth population. Today almost all countries have internet network. Since there is a large youth group in India and they use these media consistently, it helps in marketing success.
- The principle of flexibility can be maintained by using global media in marketing activities. Depending on the situation, the marketing process can be easily changed according to the customer base.
- Social media allows the marketing process to continue round the clock and all days of the week (24x7). Consumers, applied consumer segments can view this medium at their convenience. No special effort is required for this. This is easily possible due to internet and social media.

Types of Social Media Marketing

Facebook Marketing:

Facebook is the biggest networking site in the social media in present times and through it can provide a lot of momentum to the business. When marketing through Facebook, we may post photos, videos, or other descriptive information about your business. At the same time, we can communicate with our customers to a certain extent through digital marketing of this medium. Also through this medium we can allow people to like and share to attract the products we have. We can also give information to the customers through this medium about the offers that we can give to the customers through the business.

This tool that can communicate and provide multiple product information to customers simultaneously makes marketing activities more effective. While using this medium for business, various customers get many products that they like and need on this site. Currently Facebook has 2.27 billion active members. Through Facebook advertising, the manager can reach the potential customers or target audience at once. Through Facebook, a manager can get information about the location, age, gender, education level, relationship status, employment information, preferences, and purchasing behaviour of the target audience.

Custom Audiences can be created through Facebook such as phone number, email as well. Custom audience is created through phone number, e-mail. Facebook Marketing is a platform that helps in spreading various product advertisements and information to many people simultaneously. Over the past decade, Facebook has transformed into the largest social media marketplace.

Advantages of Facebook Marketing:

- All kinds of information is provided at one place from Facebook page. Also, all the information reaches the customers in a single form. Similar to mediums like Twitter or Instagram, Facebook makes more interactive advertising available to consumers.
- Through this platform, the company, which is its respondent class, visits the website of the respective product. Also, because of these customers, the company's website receives high quality leads. As a result, more trust is created in the mind of the customer towards the company. Similarly, the company can also request customers to visit more other products on its website.
- Businesses get more business opportunities through Facebook. Because through Facebook, an entrepreneur or businessman can provide information about more of his products in a good way. Advertisements placed on this platform can be both verbal and visual. A

company can drive more growth in their posts through promotional videos.

- Marketing through Facebook is one of the best options available for small businesses that do not have their own website. Such businessmen can upload their product information on the Facebook page and for a long time this advertisement will be continuously visible to the customers. As a result, the advertisement reaches the maximum target community. Advertising of the product on Facebook does not incur any cost. Facebook ads are affordable and reachable to everyone. Facebook ads are charged on two bases CPM and CPC. CPM stands for Cost Per Thousand Impressions while CPC stands for Cost Per Click of an ad. A businessman can set his daily budget for this advertising fee.
- Facebook can also establish an instant and easy interaction between consumers and related businesses. The business listens to what the customers have to say and responds promptly to the customers. As a result, the credibility of that brand increases in the minds of customers. Today's young generation prefers online shopping through Facebook.
- Nowadays, many people are establishing contact with various brands through social media. Due to this the phone calls are also delayed. A chatbot is created on Facebook Messenger to answer the problems of the users and solve the problems.
- Some marketers believe that social media affects search rankings. It is believed that the information required during ranking is collected by robots. Similarly, the extent to which an industry-business organization is active on social media also affects it. Shares, likes and comments provide information on the extent to which a related site is popular and trusted.

Tweeter Marketing:

Twitter is a source of instant information on current events, trends and business debates. The class that uses it is mainly the youth class. As a result, various events that are currently going on and discussed through business are commented on. A clear and detailed review of various business affairs is taken through it. As the negative and positive feedback of the customers through Vitter reaches the industry business organization immediately, the concerned company can make necessary changes in the services offered to the customers.

People who have two accounts have the knowledge of what is happening all over the world regarding a particular topic. On average, 500 million tweets are sent through a Twitter account every day. Due to which many business people are looking for their business opportunities through Tweeter. The task of spreading the name of the

business organization all over the world is easily done through Tweeter. A discussion on a Twitter account is like a face-to-face discussion between a company and a customer. If the company's product content on Twitter is engaging, then the company attracts many new customers resulting in brand awareness.

Advantages of Twitter Marketing:

- Reach a large target community: Twitter's user base is very large, which allows the company to reach potential customers relatively quickly. As a result, followers or advocates of the company reach more customers by using hash tags.
- Delivery of customer services: Through this platform, the two-way communication activity takes place directly with the customers, thereby increasing the interactions with the people. Through this interaction and communication, the company sees a positive way of doing business.
- Introduction to the brand: : Communicates through the brand and ethics and personality. This helps the business to reach the target community.
- Useful information can be collected through feedback given by customers through Twitter.
- Opening an account on Twitter is free. Paid ads are available. Many businesses have benefited from this post

Instagram Marketing:

Instagram Marketing is a popular social media platform. Every small businessman can use this platform to expand his business. Through this, businessmen can upload photos of their products on this account. This medium also provides some tools for professional marketing. Businesses use their Instagram account to grow their customer base. Businesses promote their products and services on Instagram with the help of proper marketing strategies. Also, their brand is also popularized and their sales are increased.

Instagram marketing is a way to reach the customers and through this social platform the business is brought to many customers. Just like Facebook and Twitter, anyone can open an Instagram account. The user can also communicate with others. Also can send private messages and upload photos and videos. Hosts native filters that users can add to their photos. These present filters make various changes to the photo, including adding light, toning the image, increasing or decreasing saturation, and more. Additionally, users can edit images directly within the platform instead of using third-party photo editors. If they don't like a particular filter, they can use Instagram's editing feature to independently change contrast, brightness, composition, warmth, saturation, sharpness, and more.

Benefits of Instagram Marketing:

- According to people on Instagram, their most profitable platform for social media activism is Instagram. Currently there are 800 million active users on Instagram. Out of them 500 users use this platform daily. 80% of them are from outside the US. 34% of these people are affluent and affluent and 38% are site-checkers for various reasons throughout the day. As a result, while starting a business through Instagram, there is no limit to its success.
- Instagram marketing is beneficial for any type of business and its success. Due to the extremely wide reach, business information reaches maximum number of people. Even a small company can advertise its business on it. All companies, from small to large companies, can maximize their marketing efforts on Instagram if they plan and execute their marketing strategies properly.
- Instagram has evolved through many stages and has become able to generate money through products in the present time. As a result, money is made available through various products through Instagram.
- Instagram is one of the best platforms to find potential customers. Live posts and stories can be added through these many features. As a result, there are videos related to some stories or products. If a video is made of how the product is made, how the office staff works, to reach the customers consistently, the trust that people have about the brand increases. Instagram's live videos are useful for building business relationships in the minds of customers, building loyalty and trust in brand, and interacting with actual company representatives and customers.

Advantages of Social Media in Marketing System

- Social media makes it possible to capture a large market geographically. The expanding network of internet, mobile revolution has boosted the marketing process of the business organizations in large market as well as around the world. Similarly, different types of marketing can be done in different markets according to the needs and nature of the market
- Sales volume is essential for business growth. For that, the business organization has to enter new markets. Some business organizations are already working there. They may even be popular. In such a situation, the business organization can easily do the marketing process in the new market by making good use of social media. Due to the competition in the business sector, the work is being done to capture new markets through marketing very aggressively.

- Modern technology is used in social media. This allows the marketing message to be delivered quickly, clearly, in the best format, at the right time to the target audience. Similarly, it can be changed according to place and time. The messages conveyed through these mediums can be very effective. This benefits the business organizations for increasing profits.
- Marketing done in social media is a kind of guidance regarding the utility and use of goods and services. Marketing includes the complete analysis of when and how to use the product, how to handle, not to handle and what is the use. Similarly, the importance of objects, some guidelines for young children are included. This makes it possible for customers to use such products easily and enjoy them fully.
- These specific types of media enable the business organization to stay in touch with the customers and the market at all times. Product changes; emphasis on technology; Information about changes in colour, size, weight and price reached the customers quickly and clearly. Due to this, the business organization can remain in the mind of the customers forever. Along with this, market information can be obtained. Customer Feedback By knowing the buying order or preference of the expected customers, the business organization can decide the marketing strategy for the future.
- May remain with businesses and consumers permanently. Similarly, if there is any change in the marketing message at a low cost and in a short time, it can be brought to the attention of everyone quickly. The message can be delivered easily and cost-effectively to various markets and to a large target audience. Further marketing planning can be done at low cost by properly handling all the information (data) of customers and prospective customers.
- These types of media enable large marketing work to be done in less time. The popularity of social media, the ever-increasing use of the Internet, and the Internet not only make marketing faster and clearer, but messages can easily reach many people within seconds.

Limitations of Social Media Marketing System:

- For this type of media, some rules and laws have been laid down in various countries today. Due to some cases of cheating and some offensive content being circulated, strict rules are coming in the present time and it is expected in the future as well. It is necessary to follow this strictly now. Due to intense competition, various social media have made some unwritten rules or fixed some policies. This limits the marketing sector.

- Today's consumer and prospective consumer segments ignore social media marketing due to overuse and constant marketing messages. Often such messages and information are not seen. The customer class does not even provide priority feedback. Therefore, social media marketing activities are limited.
- Due to the easy and full-time availability of different types of media, huge popularity, constant use of the internet, there is fierce competition in either media itself. But there is fierce competition in the marketing field as well. Due to this, the business organization has to constantly monitor other contacts. Not only has this, but the developments of the markets had to be monitored. We have to continuously attract the expected customer base. Sometimes the marketing function has to change rapidly. Intrusion into private life: The increasing use of mass media, constant contact
- Marketing messages, aggressive advertising has led to criticism that such matters intrude into people's private lives. This expert class demands a large amount of business as they work in a professional manner and without their help a good
- These types of media networks are found all over the world and are widely used by business organizations at major ports. Many times this work is done in English so the message or marketing information is not easily or well understood by the customers.

Summary:

The use of social media in India is very extensive. One of the largest economies in the world, a large market as well as a large proportion of young population are attracting large businesses of the world to India. Today, the media of the world has made it convenient for them to come to India and popularize the product.

Almost all the small and big entrepreneurs of the country use these media. According to a survey, Facebook has become the most popular type of marketing medium in India and is seen to be receiving a massive response. Facebook, Instagram, YouTube and Twitter are widely used in India

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